

Notas breves

First Mediterranean record of *Rhodope rosloi* Haszprunar & Hess, 2005 (Gastropoda: Heterobranchia: Rhodopidae)

Primera cita para el Mediterráneo de *Rhodope rosloi* Haszprunar & Hess, 2005 (Gastropoda: Heterobranchia: Rhodopidae)

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PALABRAS CLAVE: *Rhodope*, Mediterráneo, Granada, Heterobranquio.

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Rhodope* Koelliker, 1847 comprises minute, worm-like gastropods with highly simplified morphology and historically uncertain phylogenetic placement. Long considered controversial due to the absence of shell, foot, radula, and gills, Rhodopemorpha are now resolved as basal heterobranchs within the clade Allomorpha, sister to the shelled Murchisonellidae (WILSON ET AL., 2017). Moreover, a new superfamily Tjaernoioidea was erected by BRENZINGER, SCHRÖDL & KANO (2021), containing the families Tjaernoioiidae and Parvaplustridae, strongly supported sister to Allomorpha. Thus, these authors erected the new infraclass Mesoneura (for the clade Tjaernoioidea + Allomorpha), a novel taxon in a phy-

logenetic position between the diverse clade Euthyneura and the less-diverse grade of 'lower' heterobranchs (BREZZINGER ET AL., 2021).

These meiofaunal molluscs exhibit extreme morphological reduction, including vermiform bodies, subepidermal spicules, and the absence of copulatory organs (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991; BREZZINGER, HASZPRUNAR & SCHRÖDL, 2013).

Eight valid species are currently accepted within the genus: *Rhodope veranii* Koelliker, 1847, *R. crucispiculata* Salvini-Plawen, 1991, *R. marcusii* Salvini-Plawen, 1991, *R. transtrosa* Salvini-Plawen, 1991, *R. rousei* Brenzinger, Wilson & Schrödl, 2011, *R. placozophagus* Cuervo-González, 2017, *R. rosloi*

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Haszprunar & Hess, 2005, and *R. salvini-plaweni* Fernández-Simón & Moles, 2025. Of these, three species have been previously recorded in the Mediterranean Sea, *R. veranii*, originally described from Sicily and later found in Croatia and northeastern Spain, *R. crucispiculata*, described from Tunisia (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991) and *R. salvini-plaweni*, recently described from Catalonia (FERNÁNDEZ-SIMÓN, SALVADOR & MOLES, 2025).

Rhodope roskoi was described from Roscoff (France), based on specimens collected from shelly gravel at 25 m depth (HASZPRUNAR & HESS, 2005). It is distinguished by its small size (approximately 1.5 mm), translucent white body, and a diagnostic orange transverse band behind the head and a longitudinal dorsal stripe. In this note, we formally report *Rhodope roskoi* from the Mediterranean coast of southern Spain, based on live specimens photographed in 2024. This record represents the fourth Mediterranean species of *Rhodope*, and the first formal documentation of *R. roskoi* in this basin.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We report the first confirmed Mediterranean record of *R. roskoi*, based on two live specimens observed in Velilla (Almuñécar, Granada, Spain; 36.741242°N, 3.664873°W), under rocks in shallow subtidal sediment.

Specimens photographed (not collected): SPAIN – Andalucía • 1 specimen; Almuñécar, Velilla beach, Granada; 36.741242°N, 3.664873°W; 7 m depth; 7 Sep. 2024; David Ballesteros leg.; photographed in situ; no voucher specimen deposited. • 1 specimen; Almuñécar, Velilla beach, Granada; 36.741242°N, 3.664873°W; 4 m depth; 18 Sep. 2025; Luis Sánchez-Tocino leg.; photographed and video recorded in situ; no voucher specimen deposited.

A short video of the second individual is available in the supplementary material <<https://zenodo.org/records/17829385>>. The habitat (coarse sediment

and rocky substrate in shallow subtidal zones) matches that described for *R. roskoi* and other Rhodopidae (HASZPRUNAR & HESS, 2005). The morphological traits visible in the photographs (Figure 1) and video, including the distinctive coloration pattern, are consistent across both individuals and agree with the original description and published images (HASZPRUNAR & HESS, 2005). No other described *Rhodope* species exhibits this exact combination of features.

The specimens exhibited slow, gliding locomotion across the substrate (original video uploaded to <<http://www.litoraldegranada.ugr.es>> the 18th of September 2025), with smooth and careful movement, minimal body deformation, and no visible foot or tentacles. Notably, the second specimen occasionally lifted its anterior region slightly above the substrate in a manner reminiscent of chemosensory endings observed in nudibranchs. Although *R. roskoi* lacks rhinophores, *Rhodope* species retain a double rhinophoral nerve, homologous to Hancock's organ of other opisthobranchs, which originates from the cerebral ganglion and innervates the anterior body wall (SALVINI-PLAWEN, 1991; BRENZINGER ET AL., 2013). This behavior may reflect substrate exploration or environmental sensing through its anterior body part.

Species of *Rhodope* are known to inhabit interstitial environments and may feed on sponge larvae or placozoans (CUERVO-GONZÁLEZ, 2017; EITEL ET AL., 2024; RIEDL, 1959). Recent genomic studies have shown that Rhodopidae harbour placozoan DNA in their digestive tract, suggesting a specialized predator-prey relationship (EITEL ET AL., 2024). The presence of *R. roskoi* in Almuñécar may therefore indicate overlooked placozoan diversity in Mediterranean sediments. Its detection in the Alborán Sea expands the known range of the species beyond its original Atlantic locality and supports the hypothesis that Rhodopemorphs are more widespread than currently documented (WILSON ET AL., 2017).

Figure 1. Images of the two specimens photographed in Almuñécar (Granada, Spain). A: map with the location of the new citation; B: individual photographed on 7 September 2024 (©David Ballesteros); C, D: individual photographed on 18 September 2025 (©Luis Sánchez Tocino). The sketches below the images represent a comparison of *Rhodope* species modified from HASZPRUNAR & HESS, 2005. Arrows indicate the deformation of the horizontal orange band of *Rhodope roskei* when it is on the move.

Figura 1. Imágenes de los dos individuos fotografiados en Almuñécar (Granada, España). A: mapa con la ubicación de la nueva cita; B: individuo fotografiado el 7 de septiembre de 2024 (©David Ballesteros); C, D: individuo fotografiado el 18 de septiembre de 2025 (©Luis Sánchez Tocino). Los bocetos bajo las fotografías representan la comparación de especies de *Rhodope* modificada de HASZPRUNAR & HESS, 2005. Las flechas indican la deformación de la banda naranja horizontal de *Rhodope roskei* cuando está en movimiento.

CONCLUSION

The discovery of *Rhodope roskei* in Velilla (Almuñécar) adds a new species to the Mediterranean and Spanish mala-

cofauna and highlights the importance of photographic documentation in detecting cryptic interstitial taxa. Future molecular studies may clarify its trophic role and reveal associated placozoan lin-

eages, following the “catch-by-slug” approach proposed by EITEL *ET AL.* (2024).

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Supplementary Video: *Rhodope roskei* behaviour. <<https://zenodo.org/records/17829385>>